

The potential for Local Authorities to contribute to Climate Protection and Greenhouse Effect Prevention. A review of ten Municipalities on the island of Rhodes, Greece.

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This paper explores Climate Protection at a local level. Initially it was essential to define and understand the "Greenhouse Effect" before evaluating local authorities' potential to counteract it. We examined strategies dealing with the problem of climate change and particular emphasis was placed on the potential for local authorities to exert an influence. We examined the frameworks, policies, challenges, problems and best practices for climate protection at a local level. Our research examined ten municipalities on the island of Rhodes in Greece and assessed their current contribution to climate protection. Results showed that all ten municipalities implement a range of measures to protect the climate and reduce CO₂ emissions.

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1. Introduction

Human settlements have been developing for thousands years in a variety of forms (Cities, Towns and Villages) depending on the local conditions, geography, climate, population size, trade, and wars. Up to the 18th century the cities all around the world were simply compact communities that brought together people, goods, and services. The change in the role of cities following the industrial revolution, the consequences of the new industries expanding use of available fossil fuel, created the potential for high levels of pollution. Indeed, today, energy consumption per capita is still increasing in every industrial country. Accordingly, cities have become major polluters producing astonishing amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other emissions harmful to the environment and public health.

2. Climate change

Scientists' concern for the greenhouse effect has been increased worldwide since the early seventies. In 1988 the United Nations in collaboration with many national environmental delegations conducted a general evaluation of the climate change phenomenon, its likely results, and appropriate political responses. This initiative is now known as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

According to scientists a most likely future scenario would be that increasing greenhouse gas emissions could alter the climate to an unstable pre-glacier era. The climate does not follow a linear course. It is characterized by sudden and dramatic changes and therefore is not known what will happen if we reach certain critical points as a result of an increase of greenhouse gas levels in the atmosphere. (Bjorke and Seki, 1999. p. 9)

Having researched the stages through which Earth's climate has passed over millions of years, today scientists would describe Earth's climate as passing through a "warm" period. The forecasted increase in the Earth's temperature of 0,3C per decade (Houghton et al 1992, p. 17) will be the most intense rate of increase that has faced the planet in the last 10.000 years.

The concern of scientists is focused in the rhythm of increase and on whether the ecosystems will have enough time to adapt to the new situation. The increases in temperature may lead to the collapse of natural systems, result in the disappearance of certain species, and finally weaken the support of the biosphere (Common, 1995, p. 282).

3. New possibilities for local action

Climate change issues bring to the surface the need to comprehend the problems that arise where natural environment and socio-economic factors interact and similarly where science and policy interact (Downing et al, 2000, p. 198-199). Climate change is an extraordinary, if not unique case, in environmental management. Instead of combating an existing environmental crisis, policies are aimed at preventing a problem arising, according to certain scientists¹. The processes that lead to the change of climate are not fully understood. We still lack a widely acceptable theory that is inclusive of all the factors involved².

Social sciences³ have developed many theories on climate change and yet we do not have one that is sufficiently adequate to describe the process, the causes and the outcomes. Respectable scientists attempt to describe climate change as mainly influenced by the behavior of social systems. Natural and social systems are characterized by their enormous complexity and the interaction between them increases this complexity. Moreover, information available to policy-making institutions is distorted by uncertainties due to errors in measurement and conceptual ambiguities.

Understanding and accurately predicting global climate change is still beyond any comprehensive and reliable scientific measure. The usual approaches of natural sciences, direct experimentation and forecast models, are not effective when used in

¹ IPCC Second Assessment Report: Climate Change 1995. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 1996.

² Schellnhuber, H.J. 'Earth system' analysis and the second Copernican revolution. Nature 402 (6761), 1999.

³ Rayner, S. and Malone, E.L.. Human Choices and Climate Change. Volume1: The Societal Framework. Batelle Press, Columbus, Ohio, 1998.

the context of global environmental threats such as climate change. According to Downing, a new base is required for the application of environmental policy.

Currently, scientists⁴ are proposing the development of a simulation model, which will include all the factors involved in climate change (participatory agent - based social simulation model). This model will examine the ways in which social structures result from interactions between individuals and how in turn these structures influence and limit the behavior of individuals, thereby changing or strengthening social structures. The advantage of this method is that it analyses the problem from the viewpoint of the sociologist, anthropologist and natural scientist.

The difficulty in linking a global problem to local factors is now recognized, and there is interesting research being developed in this area that attempts to relate global issues to local ones (global to local). We have a study (Wilbanks and Cadis, 1999, p. 618) where three main research questions are put forward challenging the "top → down" approach of mainstream research and incorporating the alternative views of "bottom → up" research, in order to improve the scientific community's understanding of the importance of local **factors**:

- (1) Could we use a "top → down" research paradigm at the local level?
- (2) Could a convergence of viewpoints between global and local perspectives diminish? or be used for the better understanding of global climate change?
- (3) What could/would Municipalities do that would have an impact on global climate change?

4. Potential for action by the municipalities

The potential role of Local initiatives for climate protection was identified only very recently, in fact only in the last decade. Now, international organizations such as the UN⁵, Institutions and Research Centers, Governments, Regional as well as Local Authorities have become aware of the potential of locally based initiatives.

⁴ DOWNING et al, (2000), Understanding Climate Policy Using Participatory Agent-Based Social Simulation

⁵ ICLEI, Local Government Implementation of Climate Protection, Report to United nations,

In 2000 the Dutch Energy Center ECN together with the “Center for Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy” CSTM of the University of Twente⁶ carried out a research project "Local Government and Climate Policy". The research brought to the light the desire of many Local Authorities in the Netherlands to improve their environmental policy making and to take on more responsibilities in that area. In 2000 one in six Municipalities had committed to decrease emissions of CO₂ to 50% of the 1987 emission levels by 2010. Also one in four Municipalities have agreed to implement Chapter 28 of Agenda 21, which was decided in Rio, and to set up a Local Agenda 21.

Given the fact that a Local Authority is the form of government closest to the citizens, and has a lot of discretion concerning activities that influence the environment⁷ and accordingly climate change - such as waste management, public transportation etc. we thought it appropriate to pose the following question:

- Is it possible to **measure** Local Authorities contribution to the climate protection?

Naturally all Local Authorities do not have at their disposal the same resources or opportunities to influence or plan their climate protection policy. Initiatives and actions by each Municipality depend on factors such as the size, growth, traffic patterns of their area etc. but also on the extent to which they are legally empowered to plan and to implement for climate protection.

Therefore our main research question could be analyzed as follows:

1. How could municipalities **influence greenhouse gas emissions** on a national level?
2. What are the **restrictions** on the implementation of a local climate protection policy?
3. How are local climate policies **influenced by** energy liberalization, local policies and participative decision-making?

December 1997

⁶In the framework of Dutch *research Program for the Pollution of Atmosphere and the Climatic Change*. (Burger *et al* 2000)

⁷(Spanou 1998, p. 153)

4. Is it possible to **incorporate** climate protection policies to all local authority activities?

Generally according to Collier and Löfstedt⁸ environmental policy in Europe adopts a hierarchic approach; decisions are taken at the top (in national or European level) and then finally implemented at regional or local level. Nevertheless, the local authority still has a certain influence and competence in certain critical fields. Actually what we have is a conflict between independent local policies and imposed governmental measures. As it happens, certain decisions are taken exclusively by Municipal Councils thus leaving an opportunity window for the existence of a *local climate protection policy*.

Supplying basic municipal services often involves complex distribution, processing, and procurement systems. For example, supplying clean water to inhabitants requires a whole range of activities. Sourcing, purifying distributing the clean water and disposal or recycling of waste water. All these functions have different climate change impacts, depending on how the services are performed. Municipalities directly control decisions that affect greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which come from municipal operations, the inhabitant waste stream and landfill sites. Through a range of policy tools, municipalities also have the power to influence levels of the GHG emissions that come from the community at large. According to a Canadian Government report, municipalities control, both directly and indirectly, more than half of total GHG emissions that are released in Canada⁹.

5. Setting up a Local Action Plan

In order for a municipality to launch a climate protection policy it should initially begin with a vision for the future, then identify the objectives, continue with programs

⁸ Collier and Löfstedt, 1997, p. 25

⁹ Municipalities Issue Table of Canada's National Climate Change Process. 1999. Municipalities Table Options Paper. December 1999. p. 18.

and concrete measures and finally set up monitoring mechanisms. In other words create a climate management system in accordance with environmental management systems (ISO 14000, EMAS).

Burger¹⁰ defines this Municipal climate management as "the organizational structure, responsibilities, procedures, processes and the sources for determining and implementing local government climate policy" and proposes a 6 step approach for the establishment of a Municipal climate policy. These six steps have been inspired by quality management systems. They include:

1. A binding document - decision by the Local Government on climate protection
2. Plans and programs for the application of this policy inside and outside the Organization
3. Integration of these plans into the daily operations and organizational culture
4. Measuring, checking and reconsideration of Municipality's climate protection performance
5. Offering education and training to increase understanding of climate problems
6. Publishing information concerning Municipality's climate protection performance

The International Council of Environmental Initiatives ICLEI¹¹, connecting Local Agenda 21 process to climate protection, proposes a similar process of 5 steps: development of an energy and emissions inventory in the Municipality, establishment of an emissions target, an action plan set up and approved by the Municipal Council, implementation of policies and measures and monitoring of the results. This methodology was applied in two campaigns: "Urban CO₂ Reduction Project" and CCP "Cities for Climate Protection", where more than 180 local authorities worldwide, followed a process in order to develop local action plans. Using this methodology, most of these Municipalities successfully developed and adopted 2-year action-plans, which today are being implemented.

¹⁰ BURGER H., COENEN F., MENKVELD M., Local Government and Climate Policy. National research Program for global air pollution. Netherlands, 2000, p. 9

¹¹ ICLEI, 1995, p. 43-44

6. Problems and difficulties

Lack of information, while important for decision makers, is not the main obstacle a Local Authority faces in the development of a climate protection policy. Various institutional impediments do exist and make it exceptionally difficult for the Municipality to deal with global warming at a local level and apply concrete policies and measures.

Firstly, the organizational structure of a Municipality does not currently normally include an active organizational unit for the purpose of climate protection. Besides, most local authorities lack the administrative capacity or the know-how for planning measures that prevent GHG emissions. In most cases the necessary personnel is not available or does not have the appropriate qualifications or specialization that is required for the control and the analysis of GHG emissions. Last but not least, most Municipalities are not willing, or are unable, to invest part of their budget for climate protection. Some investments (e.g. renewable energy) require significant funds. (Betsill 2000, p. 18-19)

Generally a Local Authority's ability to act depends on a variety of factors such as the governance system (centralization or decentralization) and the level of de-regulation in the energy market. In Greece, although in 2000 there was an attempt to unite small villages and communities into larger and stronger Municipalities, they still remain powerless to develop an independent environmental policy (Spanou 1998, p. 154). The role attributed to them by the state is advisory or ancillary and they have a only a consultative function on environmental issues and land use planning.

Climate change, as with most environmental problems, requires a holistic view and a lot of collaboration between sectors. However this is not the norm in the public sector where, usually there exists an explicit segregation in services, departments and offices with defined mandates and personnel with defined tasks. A climate protection policy would involve co-operation in such areas as waste management, transport, public works land use planning for example. However the officials that work in these areas

hardly ever sit at the same table in the average Municipality (Nijkamp and Perrels, 1994, p.124).

Furthermore, where there is no Environmental Department or a Local Agenda 21 Coordinator, many Municipalities “accommodate” climate protection activities within the Technical Department and assign engineers or city planners to coordinate the program. Traditionally municipal engineers do not view environmental protection as part of their specific responsibilities and therefore there is a tangible risk that the necessary appropriately skilled human resources will not be allocated to climate protection (Betsill 2000, p. 19).

7. Best Practice

In 1990 officials from European cities met with colleagues working in the Amazon area and decided to create the "Climate Alliance for the Protection of the Atmosphere and earth" (Klima-Bundnis / Alianza del Clima) with its headquarters in Frankfurt am Main in Germany. Their objective was to proceed with measures at a local level instead of patiently waiting for international climate protection initiatives and the protection of the Amazon forest. So even before the setting up of IPCC and the Kyoto protocol Climate Alliance had already demonstrated 100 action-plans (projects) in member Municipalities for the protection of the climate. This initiative continues today and its members now exceed seven hundred compared to the initial fourteen.

Climate Alliance¹² has developed a methodology, which consists of 10 Steps that a Municipality should follow in order to set up a comprehensive strategy for the protection of climate. However, its most significant accomplishment is a list of 150 "measures that offer a practical guide for Municipalities to protect the climate. Climate Alliance members submit, on a regular basis, reports of the plans, activities and results they are able to demonstrate. These reports give a clear picture of the progress achieved by the members of alliance all around the world and the contribution of individual Municipalities.

¹² In the framework of the international research program "Optimizing the Climate Protection Strategies of Local Authorities in Europe"

The list of measures is structured according to the main roles played by local authority:

- **The local authority as consumer and model**
- **The local authority as planner and regulator**
- **The local authority as supplier and provider**
- **The local authority as advisor and promoter**

8. Case Study: 10 Municipalities Rhodes Greece

Theoretical background

Our research within the 10 municipalities that form the island of Rhodes is based on an existing theoretical background as described earlier in this paper and we attempt to analyze and give answers to the following 3 questions:

- How could municipalities **influence greenhouse gas emissions**?
- What are the **measures** currently being implemented **towards** a local climate protection policy?
- Is it possible to **incorporate** climate protection policies into all municipal areas of activity

Methodology of research

For our research we used, with their permission, the questionnaire first developed by the European Secretariat of Klima-BUNDIS /Alianza of del Clima, in 1995 and later refined in 2000. This questionnaire is used to record the member's regular reports of plans, activities and results achieved. It was translated into Greek and it was adapted suitably in order to serve the aims and objectives of the present research.

The questionnaire includes **126 "potential measures"** that the Municipalities could adopt in energy, transport, waste management etc and is structured around the four main roles of the Municipality.

Table 1. Structure of Research Questionnaire in 10 Municipalities of Rhodes

ROLE OF MUNICIPALITY	SPHERE OF ACTION
I. THE MUNICIPALITY AS CONSUMER AND MODEL	a) Energy b) Transport c) Procurement and waste management
II. THE MUNICIPALITY AS PLANNER AND REGULATOR	a) Urban Development b) Transport
III. THE MUNICIPALITY AS SUPPLIER AND PROVIDER	a) Energy supply b) Local Public transport c) Infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists d) Waste separation and Recycling
IV. THE MUNICIPALITY AS ADVISOR AND PROMOTER	a) Energy b) Agriculture and forestry c) Cooperation with commerce and industry d) Public education & awareness-raising e) Advice e) Cooperation and participation

The questionnaire aims:

- to report Municipality's results and progress
- to help the Municipality to develop a climate protection policy
- to function as a pool for ideas

Employees in Kalithea Municipality first tested the questionnaire in order to determine whether it was suitable to our research. Their remarks were taken under consideration and the necessary improvements were made until it took its final form.

Indicators

In 1999 the KLIMA - BUNDIS / Alianza del Clima members, decided in their annual assembly on the adoption of common indicators. In our questionnaire these 21 indicators were incorporated to offer a comprehensive picture of each Municipality and the initiatives that it adopts.

Table 2. Indicators of Local Climate Protection

INDICATOR 1	% Reduction of energy consumption in Municipal buildings
INDICATOR 2	Budget for municipal energy management per inhabitant
INDICATOR 3	Settlement Density
INDICATOR 4	Percentage of 30 km/hour and traffic-calmed zones in the total of urban road network
INDICATOR 5	Share of managed parking space in total parking space
INDICATOR 6	Electricity Consumption per inhabitant per year
INDICATOR 7	m ² of solar collectors/1000 inhabitants
INDICATOR 8	Photovoltaic capacity installed/1000 inhabitant
INDICATOR 9	Share of CHP electricity in the total electricity consumption
INDICATOR 10	Capacity utilization of local public transport systems
INDICATOR 11	Length of cycle route network per inhabitant
INDICATOR 12	Modal split (private motor vehicle, public transport, cycling, walking)
INDICATOR 13	Municipal Solid waste per inhabitant per year % Recycled
INDICATOR 14	Level of grants for energy conservation and renewable per inhabitant per year
INDICATOR 15	Share of farmland managed to certified organic standards in total farmland area %
INDICATOR 16	Share of companies/sites certified pursuant to the EU EMAS scheme or DIN 14001 in total number of companies %
INDICATOR 19	Number of publications and press releases per 1000 inhabitants per year
INDICATOR 20	Number of events for the protection of climate per 1000 inhabitants per year
INDICATOR 21	Advice- days where were given advices for climate protection of per 1000 inhabitants per year

Source: Klima-BUNDIS 1999

Sample

The research was carried out in the island of Rhodes in the 10 Municipalities into which the island is administratively separated. The questionnaire was addressed to the Mayor of each Municipality and was delivered to them personally in every case. Each Mayor assigned the completion of the questionnaires to an administrator or, in one case, to the Vice-Mayor in charge of Technical matters. When we returned to collect them, some city representatives only answered them in our presence. We relied on each municipality supplying us with authentic information.

The questionnaire was also sent via email to a random sample of other municipalities in Greece so that we would have an objective analysis of the results and an evaluation on other cities performance. In this case we made no personal contact. Our goal was

to see if other municipalities could reply to the criteria questions. We received two completed questionnaires from the cities of Trikala and Koridalos-Athens.

Rhodes Island, short description

Rhodes is the biggest island of the Dodekanissa ["12 islands"] complex in the southeast Aegean Sea, with a population of 112.477. It is a popular tourist destination with 220km of coastline and a semi-mountainous landscape with its highest peak the Atavyros at 1215m.

The Rhodian cities of Ialysos, Kameiros and Lindos, as cited by Homer, fought in the Trojan War. During the Hellenistic era, Rhodes was a powerful naval force with its symbol the Colossus of Rhodes statue indicating its many victories.

The island's climate is moderate, with plenty of sunny days in summer months and a period of rainfall from October to April. More than 3.000 hours of sunshine are recorded annually and there are strong north to south winds.

The island is richly covered with forests of pines, cypresses, wild olive trees, cedars, and shrubs (oregano, thyme, levanter). Indigenous species are also found such as the small deer of Rhodes (dama dama), the butterfly of Rhodes (panaxia quadripunctata) and the endangered lake fish gizani (Ladiocypris ghighi).

The island's economy is based almost entirely on tourism with more than 70% of employment directed to the tertiary sector (services) and specifically to Tourism. It may be helpful to state that the per capita income on the island is almost the highest in Greece

Rhodes island is divided in 10 Municipalities, from which the city of **Rhodes** is the largest with **Kalithea** and **Ialysos** to follow. **Lindos** is a mainly tourist destination with no large indigenous population. **Atavyros**, **kameiros** and **Southern Rhodes** are sparsely populated and mainly rural economies. **Afantou**, **Archangelos** and **Petaloudes** are self standing economies partially relying on tourism.

Results

The questionnaire analysis showed that 294 climate protection measures are implemented in Rhodes by Local Authorities. It is an impressive number, which shows that an average of 29,4 measures are implemented by each municipality or 23,3% of total measures (see table 3). The distribution of measures' implementation is normal with the majority of Municipalities implementing in the 30-39 measures range (see graph 4.).

Table 3. Results in the total of questionnaires

DESCRIPTION	Rhodes	Kalitheia	Ialysos	Afantou	Petaloudes	Archangelos	Kameiros	Atavyros	Lindos	Southern Rhodes	TOTAL	AVERAGE
Total number of measures implemented	37	48	13	23	29	31	27	30	38	18	294	29,4
% Of measures implemented	29,4	38,1	10,3	18,3	23,0	24,6	21,4	23,8	30,2	14,3		23,3%

Tsakmakidou 2003

Tsakmakidou 2003

Regarding the spread of measures attributed to each of the 4 Roles of Local Authority we notice that that the **first group of measures** (municipality as consumer and

model) takes prominence with a 38% implementation percentage whereas the **third group** (Municipality as supplier and provider) follows with 25% (see graph 1.).

Tsakmakidou 2003

It appears (see graph 1) that municipalities tend to implement measures mostly in the first category where policies follow the top-down paradigm. Indeed in this area (as a consumer) municipality policies are dictated by the central government and municipalities have to comply with them. They also tend to be more tedious with matters when they are held accountable for (as a model).

Graph 4. Pyramid chart

Looking into the first group of measures, which examines the role of **Municipality as consumer and model**, we see that 90% of the Municipalities on the island implement, energy saving measures in the Municipal buildings and 80% of them work towards waste reduction in municipally owned enterprises (Tsakmakidou, 2003 p. 76). On the contrary hardly anyone uses renewable energy in municipally owned buildings or has modernized the energy control systems. Finally none has reviewed the existing energy supply contracts regarding the purchase of “green” energy.

In the second category, **Municipality as planner and regulator**, 70% of Municipalities support transportation patterns more conducive to livable cities by means of traffic calming, access restrictions and parking space management. Nevertheless currently only 2 Municipalities have designated bicycle lanes while none has plans in the future to use small-scale CHP units.

In the third group, **Municipality as supplier and provider**, almost all Municipalities facilitate measures on local public transport (e.g tickets sale in vehicles, roofing in bus-stops). We found that four out of the ten Municipalities provide infrastructure for pedestrians and cyclists. On the other hand, no special measures are taken for the

disposal of (H)CFCs, HFCs and PFCs, nor for the separate collection of organic waste, glass and paper and biogas utilization.

In the last group, **Municipality as advisor and promoter**, the municipalities' contribution is rather limited. Popular practices are programs in schools and experience exchanges with peer Municipalities. It is notable that four out of ten Municipalities give advice to local companies and the public, on waste management and promote education and awareness-raising on climate protection for citizens, local groups and institutions. Nevertheless, there are no grant programs for the energy sector and there are no publications or press releases on climate protection. (Tsakmakidou, 2003 p. 77).

Tsakmakidou 2003

It is interesting that Municipalities that rely mostly on category I like Southern Rhodes and Ialysos have the least number of recorded interventions (see graph 3). In other words it appears that the top-down approach is not producing the desired outcome. On the other hand, Kalithea and Lindos, the two top achievers, have a fair share of measures in all four categories thus involving the people and getting a higher score. Especially Kalithea is implementing a sound proportion of 4th category

measures including the Local Agenda 21 process, clearly following the *bottom-up* approach.

We feel obliged to state here that the Climate Alliance Questionnaire is a very good diagnostic instrument as it enables an analysis of the most productive interventions.

9. Conclusions

Climate protection initiatives do have a local as well as a global character as described in our analysis and this trend for local action has indeed a real potential in Greece. This new activism is possible mainly because local authorities in many countries currently control and implement the regulatory and economic tools that can make cities greener and energy efficient. Apart from land use planning, these tools include urban development policies, investment in infrastructure, renewable energy sources management, decision making for schools, parks, and recreation areas.

With these tools, the municipal authorities could for example:

- Encourage the use public transport.
- Legislate on energy efficiency for new buildings.
- Build cogeneration energy systems CHP
- Encourage local industry to invest in energy saving measures
- Designate areas for pedestrians and cyclists
- Plant trees and increase the amount of green space
- Prompt citizens to be more prudent in the use of energy.

Even though global warming is a hard to manage issue, local authorities could allocate a number of tools and measures in order to locally influence GHG emissions and energy use. Almost certainly in many countries Local Authorities have a wider influence on climate protection than the national government. Indeed in the future, cities will be the focal point of change, since they exercise real power and can administer at a local level and can introduce participative decision making, and innovative tools such as Local Agenda 21 in their existing and future areas of responsibility.

The choice and combination of measures that are needed, the policies, and the programs are a complex administrative and political process within the existing municipal structure. Politicians, decision makers and administrators can now turn for help to many successful and proven “best practices”.

Adapting these initiatives in an effective Local Action plan requires the collaboration and the commitment of key-persons, including the members of the Municipal council. It also requires imagination and the motivation of personnel. Local authorities that achieve this objective will enjoy the fruits of their labor, upgrade quality of life in their cities and make an important contribution to the reduction of GHG emissions for the protection of the climate.

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